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*Bridging the Gap: Access to
Finance for Refugee
Entrepreneurs in the UK*

**Elena Pershina
Phillip Davies
William Shepherd**

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About the author(s)

Elena Pershina, Philip Davies and William Shepherd are researchers at the Transformative Enterprise Research Group-TERG in Paisley, Scotland.

Route correspondence to email: Elena.pershina@uws.ac.uk

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Kingsley O Omeihe, Editor-in-Chief, TERG Working Paper Series, Paisley,
Scotland. King.omeihe@uws.ac.uk

Executive Summary

Refugee entrepreneurship offers significant economic and social benefits yet is hampered by limited access to finance. This working paper explores the financial barriers faced by refugee entrepreneurs in the UK, highlighting legal, institutional, and social constraints. It advocates for a Resource-Based View (RBV) to understand how entrepreneurs use internal resources to overcome these challenges. The paper identifies the need for targeted financial support and policy changes to promote the financial inclusion of refugee entrepreneurs, ultimately unlocking their potential to contribute to the UK economy.

Introduction

A focus on refugee entrepreneurship has emerged as a vital pathway to economic independence and social integration for displaced individuals in the United Kingdom, alongside other host nations (Osman, 2020). Through establishing businesses, refugees not only generate income for themselves and their families but also contribute to the economy of their 'host country' (Bizri, 2017), through job creation, innovation, and the enrichment of local markets with diverse products and services. Beyond economic impact, entrepreneurship enables refugees to build connections within their communities, fostering mutual understanding and reducing social barriers. Support for these entrepreneurs has been developed and implemented through the Entrepreneurial Refugee Network (TERN) (TERN, 2025) and Refugee Entrepreneurship Network (REN)(Centre for Entrepreneurs, 2024a) within the UK.

Refugees (or asylum migrants) are far more likely to be self employed than UK-born people (21% to 14%), and those self-employed refugees are also more likely to employ staff than their UK-born counterparts (24% to 18%) (Kone, Ruiz & Vargas-Silva, 2019). However, the same report also suggests the refugees are less likely to run a medium- or large- enterprise (based on number of employees), indicating that growth prospects for refugee entrepreneurs might be constrained. Given that for any entrepreneur access to finance is a critical determinant of success (Shaw et al., 2005), it seems likely that financial access might be a major cause of this constraint. Without the ability to secure loans, establish credit histories, or access traditional banking services due a lack of tangible assets (Hall and Lerner, 2010), many refugees face limitations in starting or expanding their businesses. This lack of financial inclusion not only hampers their economic potential but also undermines their ability to fully integrate into the host society.

The purpose of this paper is to explore the financial challenges faced by refugee entrepreneurs in the UK and their broader implications. It examines the systemic barriers that restrict access to finance, including legal, institutional, and social constraints, and highlights the strategies refugees employ to overcome these hurdles. By analysing these

issues, the paper aims to identify actionable policy solutions and practical measures to enhance financial inclusion for refugee entrepreneurs, ultimately unlocking their full potential as contributors to the UK's economic and social fabric.

Definition of Refugee Entrepreneurship

According to the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), refugees are individuals who have been compelled to flee their home countries due to war, violence, conflict, or persecution, seeking safety beyond their national borders. In host countries, individuals who are granted asylum status are formally recognised as refugees, granting them access to legal protections and essential support services (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, 2019). It is important to note that within this definition there is a huge variation in age, gender, education and other socio-economic and demographic factors (Reis et al., 2024)

Refugee entrepreneurship refers to the business activities undertaken by individuals who have been forcibly displaced from their home countries and seek to establish enterprises in host countries. Unlike traditional entrepreneurship, which is often driven by opportunity and resource abundance, refugee entrepreneurship is frequently shaped by necessity, as refugees face restricted access to formal employment and other economic opportunities (Baaker et al., 2016; Collins, 2017), and is perhaps the most likely group of potential entrepreneurs to be affected by the 'liabilities of smallness and foreignness' (Haq et al, 2024). A distinguishing characteristic of refugee entrepreneurship is its relationship with financial access. (Richey et al., 2021) Refugees often encounter systemic barriers to finance, such as a lack of credit history, legal restrictions, and discrimination, making their entrepreneurial journeys uniquely challenging compared to other entrepreneurs. Addressing these financial barriers is critical to unlocking their potential for economic contribution and social integration.

Access to Finance – A resource-based viewpoint

This paper advocates for the Resource-Based Viewpoint (RBV) as the most effective theoretical framework to examine access to finance for refugee entrepreneurs. RBV emphasises the importance of leveraging unique and valuable resources—such as skills, knowledge, social connections, and cultural capital—to achieve competitive advantage and overcome systemic barriers (Barney, 1991). Finance itself can be seen as an external resource that may be available to the entrepreneurs (Anwar, Shah and Khan, 2018), but is accessed through sharing of information with third parties (Hussain et al., 2024)

Refugee entrepreneurs often operate in environments with limited financial resources and restricted access to formal banking systems (GOV.UK, 2019a). However, their intangible assets, including resilience, prior entrepreneurial experience, and robust community networks, enable them to navigate these challenges. RBV allows researchers to analyse how

these resources are mobilised to compensate for financial constraints, revealing the adaptive strategies that refugee entrepreneurs employ.

An alternative approach is to explore access to finance is to utilise the framework of social capital. It emphasises the role of networks, relationships, and trust in overcoming systemic financial barriers for refugee entrepreneurs in the UK. By examining bonding social capital, it may be possible to investigate how close-knit refugee communities facilitate informal lending or shared financial support. Bridging social capital offers insight into connections with diverse groups, such as NGOs or local business networks, which may provide access to microfinance or grants. Linking social capital highlights vertical relationships with institutions like banks or government programmes, revealing how these connections influence formal financial access and inclusion.

This paper believes that the use of an RBV lens is better than a social capital approach because it emphasises the internal resources refugee entrepreneurs possess, such as skills, knowledge, and resilience, which directly impact their ability to navigate financial barriers. While social capital highlights external networks, RBV provides a more comprehensive understanding of resource mobilisation and adaptability. There may be an opportunity to bridge these concepts by looking at the agency of refugee entrepreneurs via an intersectional mixed embeddedness framework (Khademi, Essers & Van Nieuwkerk, 2024). By focusing on the internal resources of refugee entrepreneurs, RBV shifts the narrative from deficits to strengths, highlighting their capacity for innovation and resilience. This perspective provides a nuanced understanding of financial access challenges and informs targeted policies that enhance resource utilisation, bridging gaps in the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Why the need for financial access?

Access to finance is pivotal for refugee entrepreneurs, influencing their ability to achieve economic independence, scale their businesses (Newman, Schwarz and Borgia, 2014), and integrate into host communities. Economically, financial inclusion enables refugees to invest in resources, expand operations, and create jobs. Socially, it promotes interactions with host communities, fostering mutual understanding and reducing prejudice (Hussain et al., 2024). Culturally, access to finance allows refugee-owned businesses to introduce unique products and services, enriching the diversity of local markets. Strengthening financial access is thus essential not only for the success of refugee entrepreneurs but also for the broader socio-economic development of host communities.

The Challenges to Financial Access

Refugee entrepreneurs in the United Kingdom face significant challenges in accessing finance, which severely constrains their ability to start or grow businesses. These barriers are multifaceted, encompassing legal, institutional, economic, social, cultural, and psychological dimensions, but overall 'a lack of funding is perhaps the biggest stumbling block for prospective refugee entrepreneurs' (Legrain & Burrige, 2019).

One of the most pressing obstacles for refugee entrepreneurs is the restriction on access to banking services. Refugees often struggle to open business or personal bank accounts due to their immigration status, which can exclude them from the formal financial system. (Centre for Entrepreneurs, 2024b). Without bank accounts, refugees are unable to access loans or credit facilities, hindering their ability to secure start-up capital. Bureaucratic hurdles further exacerbate the problem, as complex and opaque procedures for registering businesses discourage many refugees from formalising their ventures. These barriers not only limit access to finance but also marginalise refugees from mainstream economic activities.

Economic challenges are equally significant. Refugees often lack the credit history and collateral required by traditional financial institutions, making them ineligible for conventional loans (GOV.UK, 2019b). Furthermore, limited financial literacy among some refugee entrepreneurs impedes their ability to navigate the intricacies of funding applications and loan agreements. The high-interest rates associated with informal lending or payday loans, often the only options available, place additional financial strain on refugee businesses. Access to formal microfinance programmes, which could alleviate these issues, remains limited and underdeveloped in many parts of the UK (Centre for Entrepreneurs, 2019).

Social and Cultural Barriers

Social and cultural barriers further constrain refugee entrepreneurs, although new work on the positive aspects of cultural capital for immigrant entrepreneurship demonstrates that these social and cultural barriers need to be treated with more nuance than seen as purely a negative factor (Haq et al., 2024). Discrimination and implicit biases within financial institutions can lead to unequal treatment, deterring refugees from seeking financial support. Additionally, cultural differences in understanding financial systems can create misunderstandings or distrust between refugees and financial service providers. Refugees may also find it difficult to build relationships with local institutions, further limiting their access to resources. Addressing these challenges requires targeted interventions to create an inclusive financial environment that supports refugee entrepreneurs in overcoming these systemic barriers and unlocking their potential.

A pilot for refugee entrepreneurship

The Centre for Entrepreneurs (CFE) launched a groundbreaking pilot programme to support refugee entrepreneurship in 2019 (Centre for Entrepreneurs, 2024a), supported by funds from the Home Office and The National Lottery Community Fund (GOV.UK, 2019a). This initiative provided resources to four established business support organisations, enabling them to create and deliver bespoke programmes designed to help refugees launch and sustain businesses over a one-year period. The foundation for this pilot was laid by CFE's 2018 report, *Starting Afresh: How Entrepreneurship is Transforming the Lives of Resettled Refugees* (Centre for Entrepreneurs, 2019). The report highlighted the unique entrepreneurial potential of refugees, showcasing how they can contribute significantly to the UK as business founders. It underscored the importance of tailored business support to improve the survival rates of refugee-led ventures, reduce public expenditure, and strengthen social integration (Centre for Entrepreneurs, 2024b). The UK's world-leading resettlement programmes provide sanctuary to thousands of the most vulnerable refugees every year (GOV.UK, 2019a). It is imperative to ensure these individuals are equipped with the tools to thrive in their new environment (Meister & Mauer, 2019). Programmes such as CFE's pilot initiative are crucial in empowering refugees to establish sustainable businesses, fostering integration, and enabling them to contribute meaningfully to society (GOV.UK, 2019b).

The transformative potential of refugee entrepreneurship is evident in real-world success stories. For example, Adnan Medjedovic and Edin Basic, refugees from the Bosnia, founded the London-based pizza delivery company Firezza in 2001 (Goodman, 2010). Despite significant linguistic and cultural barriers, they utilised their experience in hospitality to build a thriving business, now valued at up to £3 million (Prynn, 2013).

More recently, and using a £2,500 startup loan, Syrian refugee Razan Al Sous set up a company producing halloumi cheese, winning significant plaudits including the World Cheese Award Bronze Medal (Osman, 2020). Recognising the need to demonstrate the impact of refugee entrepreneurship, TERN marked refugee week 2024 with a series of success stories (Positive News, 2024). These examples demonstrate the immense potential of refugees to succeed as entrepreneurs, provided they are supported by inclusive and targeted interventions.

Policy and Practical Implications

Existing financial support systems for refugee entrepreneurs in the UK suffer from significant limitations. Refugees often encounter barriers to opening bank accounts and accessing credit due to restrictive eligibility criteria tied to their immigration status. There is also a lack of targeted financial products tailored to the needs of refugee entrepreneurs, leaving many reliant on informal lending networks or high-interest loans. Additionally, microfinance initiatives remain underdeveloped in the UK, and government-backed programmes do not adequately address the unique challenges faced by refugees. These

gaps not only hinder the growth of refugee-led businesses but also perpetuate economic exclusion.

Further Areas for Research

This paper recognises that there is currently a paucity of research around the academic literature in relation to access to finance for entrepreneurial refugees, in particular in relation to 'whether entrepreneurship represents a viable option for refugees or merely serves as a means to overcome xenophobia, discrimination, or precarious employment' (Reis et al., 2024). Therefore the authors propose some areas for further research that can address this gap. The UK government, alongside third-sector organisations, has initiated pilot funding programmes to support refugee entrepreneurs. Conducting detailed case studies of these initiatives would provide valuable insights into their design, implementation, and outcomes. Such research could enhance understanding of effective funding mechanisms and inform the development of more comprehensive and sustainable financial support strategies for refugee entrepreneurship.

A comparative analysis of financial access for refugee entrepreneurs in the UK and other countries with significant refugee populations could provide critical insights into best practices and context-specific challenges. By identifying successful strategies implemented elsewhere, such research could offer evidence-based recommendations for policymakers to adapt and refine approaches to financial inclusion within the UK context. Investigating the role of digital banking and fintech solutions in overcoming barriers to financial access offers a promising avenue. Digital platforms can provide refugees with alternative methods for savings, credit, and payments, potentially bypassing traditional barriers such as lack of documentation or physical access to banking services. Research in these areas will not only enhance understanding but also inform more effective policies and practices, ultimately supporting refugee entrepreneurs in achieving their full potential.

Conclusion

Refugee entrepreneurship is a vital pathway to economic independence and social integration for displaced individuals in the UK, contributing to the economy through job creation and diverse services. However, these entrepreneurs face significant barriers to financial access, stemming from legal, institutional, economic, social, and cultural factors. These obstacles include difficulty opening bank accounts, lack of credit history, and discrimination. This paper argues that a Resource-Based View (RBV) is the most effective lens to understand how refugee entrepreneurs leverage internal resources, like resilience and community networks, to overcome financial constraints, and identifies several pathways for further researching using this viewpoint. Addressing the financial challenges faced by refugee entrepreneurs requires targeted interventions, including tailored financial products and support programmes, and there is some evidence that best practice in these interventions is already being discovered in isolated pockets. By identifying and sharing these best practices that enhance financial inclusion, the UK can unlock the full potential of

refugee entrepreneurs, strengthening both their economic prospects and the broader socio-economic development of host communities. Further research is needed to explore effective funding mechanisms and digital finance opportunities

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